

From Available to Actionable Data: An Exploration of Expert and Reuser Views on Open Data

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Abstract

The level of open data re-utilization was still low ten years after the launch of the Basque Government's open data platform, when, unexpectedly, the COVID-19 pandemic struck. Suddenly, charts and infographics –fed on open data— were lingua franca; not only experts but also ordinary citizens were demanding understandable data to make decisions. The motto during the confinement was "let's flatten the curve." This article relies on participant observation of a three-day workshop, interviews with experts and open data reusers (N=15), and an analysis of urban projects that rely on open data (N=78). Data collection was conducted before the first wave and after the third wave of the COVID-19 pandemic, from November 27, 2019, to February 17, 2021, allowing researchers to make comparisons. We find that citizens are pushing for actionable open data; that is, data embedding the attributes that make them useful and usable. This includes integrating data literacy and citizens' inputs and forming interdisciplinary teams of people inside and outside the government. This article proposes a definition for actionable data, which can be scalable to other realities.

Keywords: *COVID-19, pandemic, urban technologies, citizen participation, open data, social change, data activism*

Introduction

In these pandemic times, when people hear about data, they think of the "curve," the now-famous line chart showing possible virus progressions. On June 16, 2020, the global number of deaths from COVID-19 was 433,404 (World Health Organization, 2020), and by February 11, 2021, 2.34 million people had died of the disease (World Health

Organization, 2021). This growth, swift in urban settings, filled hospitals in many cities and forced emergency rooms to slam their doors to new patients, appoint new doctors and nurses, and demand medical supplies.

In the face of the pandemic, open data feeding official and unofficial curves helped with the decision-making (Pape et al., 2021). Suddenly, infographics and charts were *lingua franca*; the collective motto during the confinement was "let's flatten the curve" (Specktor, 2020).

The open data re-utilization level was low ten years after the Basque Government's open data platform launch when the pandemic struck this community. Unexpectedly, many people were captivated by Open Data Euskadi, and its daily updates were the center of public debate. Some discrepancies between the Spanish state's Ministry of Health and Osakidetza –the independent Basque health system— created controversy. On May 14, 2020, Osakidetza removed from its catalog the information on the so-called basic reproduction number or "R0" –measuring contagiousness— by province (López, 2020). This indicator was considered the most reliable to measure the evolution of COVID-19; when the value is less than 1, it is understood that the spread is lessening (Gallagher, 2020). The last disaggregated datasets then showed that two of the three Basque territories –Araba and Gipuzkoa— had just exceeded that barrier for the first time since the pandemic's first peaked in late March (Rioja Andueza, 2020b). Figure 1 shows a tweet from a person complaining about the Basque health authorities aggregating the data.

Figure 1: An outraged tweeter on the decision to change data updates on the pandemic¹. Source: <https://twitter.com/KikePrada/status/1261223400447631360>

At a national level, people were demanding more and better open data. In June 2020, two hundred ordinary people, researchers, activists, and experts –mostly data users— signed a manifesto favoring "accessible public data for the construction of shared knowledge in times of the global pandemic" (DatosCOVID19, 2020). The declaration argued that scientists, journalists, and citizens could help if disaggregated data were accessible "in a structured, open, clearly linked, and a contextualized way" (DatosCOVID19, 2020). However, it had little echo in news media and got no answer from the government.

This article takes a bottom-up approach to explore the role of open data. Except for authors in critical data studies (e.g., Baack, 2015; Kennedy et al., 2016; Kennedy, 2016; Gutierrez, 2018) and urban studies (e.g., Desouza and Bhagwatwar, 2012; Kloeckl et al. 2012), scholarship's emphasis has been on top-down approaches to datafication.

¹ "VERY SERIOUS. 'THEY WILL ADJUST THE DATA' [sic] And we are talking about #COVID-19 and the #pandemic As what happened in the nursing homes? In #Euskadi we have already gone through the #Phase of manipulation and lies, which has been recognized by @Irekia @Gob_eus #BasqueGovernment".

There are case studies about how governments are making open data available to foster participation (e.g., Desouza and Bhagwatwar 2014; Kloeckl et al., 2012; Hemment and Townsend, 2013; Wilson and Chakraborty, 2019). But Kassen notes that most efforts to further the idea of open data participation and collaboration "are driven by traditional top-down administrative commands or directives practically without any input from members of the civil society" (2013: 512). The attention to structures has implied that awareness of the prospect of ordinary people acting on open data has been missing in specialized literature. Despite the rise of open data, it is still uncertain how data-rich cities can "enable a collaborative culture of citizen engagement to emerge" (Certomà et al., 2017: 3). The perspectives of open data reusers, minders, and scholars are pertinent as they exemplify the link between datafication and open-source culture and show how data might sustain citizens' agency "outside big government and big business" (Baack, 2015: 1).

Spanish-speaking researchers are currently busy exploring the pandemic data (e.g., Briz-Redóna and Serrano-Aroca, 2020). For instance, looking at data modelling of COVID-19 by Spanish universities, Cobarsí-Morales signals a deficit of detailed information locally (2020). Beyond Spain, Melin and colleagues analyze the pandemic's spatial evolution using self-organizing maps based on publicly available datasets (2020). Instead of focusing on what citizens do with open data, Gayozzo examines governments that gather citizen data concluding that some Asian countries' success in using surveillance techniques could be exported in the West (Gayozzo, 2020). Tracking applications that combine Global Positioning System (GPS), Bluetooth, and other data from smartphones –connecting movements, social contacts, and demographics— are being explored to make decisions on vaccination (BBC, 2018); ensure social distancing while avoiding confinement (Cecilia et al., 2020; EFE, 2020); and develop smart cities initiatives in the face of COVID-19 (Costa and Peixoto, 2020). However, this article is

focused on open data from a bottom-up perspective. It opportunistically exploits the prospect offered by the unexpected demand of open data during the pandemic to explore their relevance. The idea is not to focus on open pandemic data specifically but more generally on open data's role to define *actionable open data*.

In this analysis, we use participant observation during a three-day, pre-pandemic workshop on open data; 15 semi-structured interviews with open data experts, reusers, and practitioners conducted before the first wave and after the third wave of the COVID-19 pandemic in Spain, and a comparative analysis of 78 open data-based proposals submitted to the Open Data Ideas Awards organized by Irekia –*open* in Basque, the name of the open data facility— in 2015, 2018, and 2020. We argue that open data approaches must change from *available* to *actionable* data.

For simplicity's sake, the analysis relies on an artificial distinction between government, for-profits, and citizens. However, the reality is not simple. The cases and the interviewees in this study involve individuals (either data experts or reusers), civil servants, and representatives from for-profit and third-sector organizations. When these agents employ open data and make their applications available, they become data intermediaries. The notion of *ordinary people* –broadly understood as non-experts— in the context of data participation is debatable as a degree of expertise is required to analyze data (Kennedy et al., 2016; Gutierrez, 2019). Also, ordinary people can become skilled intermediaries in the process of reusing open data. That is why we consider the individuals who submitted proposals to the Open Data Ideas Awards ordinary people. Although they are not the same, we consider individual citizens and representatives of organized society groups as part of the same citizen cluster for simplicity's sake. The idea here is not to understand how these different groups position themselves on open data but to identify

actionable open data's salient characteristics. Thus, the main research question is, "How can *actionable open data* be defined?"

The article is organized as follows: first, based on a literature review, we tackle the theory on open data and the Basque context. Second, a methodological section discusses the methods employed. Third, the analysis section offers the results, organized to respond to the specific research questions in conversation with the literature. And finally, the discussion section tackles the main research question.

The authors elaborated the translations from Basque and Spanish into English and the tables. The originals of long verbatim citations are offered in endnotes.

Open Data and the Basque Context

Open data are understood as data –typically from public administrations— freely available to everyone in usable formats without restrictions (Open Data Handbook, 2020). These data are offered in a "structured, machine-readable, open-licensed, and well maintained" way (Wynne-Jones, 2019, para. 3). Not all *public data* –which include public administrations' data— are open since public data are often "unstructured and unruly, and its usage requirements are often vague" (Wynne-Jones, 2019, para. 4). Open data principles can be summarized as follows: Open data must be for everyone, the data people need, and data people can easily use (World Wide Web Foundation, 2017). These definitions echo the difference between *available data* and *accessible data*. Lysecki (2019) defines available data as the wealth of data resulting from a variety of sources (e.g., smartphones, computers, and sensors), which results from the process of datafication, or the omnipresent quantification of human and non-human activity (van Dijck, 2014; Mayer-Schönberger and Cukier, 2013). While available data can be massive and unfathomable, accessible data are manageable and usable (Lysecki, 2019). Namely, public data can be part of the available data affluence, but open data are always accessible.

A step further, *transformative data* are seen from a business perspective as requiring "distributed and centralized participation" and providing a "safe and compliant" environment while ensuring that "the right users have access to relevant insights in the necessary context to drive innovation" (Deloitte, 2016: 6). Although this definition does not necessarily refer to open data, it is interesting as it adds the elements of distributed participation, usefulness, and change promotion to the understanding of data. The data infrastructure can be seen as the processes, hardware, and software needed to transform data into value, while the open data infrastructure is the open portion of that infrastructure.

The pressure to open public administrations' datasets comes from the open data movement, which redefined the notions of participation by applying the open-source ethos to data employment (Baack, 2015; Wessels et al., 2017). In 2011, enthusiasm surrounded data openness globally, reported David Eaves, creator of the first open data portal in 2009 in Vancouver (2011). However, years later, these principles have not been embraced universally. A World Wide Web Foundation report indicates that governments only publish around ten percent of their data openly worldwide (2017).

Open data facilities are typically a component of the broader open government, referring to the governance mechanisms that support transparency, participation, and collaboration. That is, open data services have become an inherent part of open government. Although open government is not the same as smart government, they often go together. The former emphasizes transparency and participation, while the latter's emphasis is digital interconnection and efficiency. The ubiquity of information and communication technologies (ICTs) and the datafication of everything engendered smart cities, a smart government dimension (Anthopoulos and Reddick, 2016). "Smart" refers to "intelligent networking" of existing objects and networks enhanced through ICT systems (Von Lucke and Grosse, 2017: 4). These cities integrate the digital in most

interactions with citizens and businesses and inter-agency relationships (Melloulia et al., 2014), generating vast amounts of data, which may or may not be open. The model of government-citizens/businesses digital interaction was supposed to make administrations more productive, participative, and transparent (Melloulia et al., 2014: 1). However, controversies and obstacles emerged (Yang and Pandey, 2011). Smart government is no longer the standard, as some authors rather talk of "smart citizens" (Hemment and Townsend, 2013), "emancipatory urbanism" (Lees, 2004), and "experiential government" (Dunleavy and Margetts, 2015). Hemment and Townsend (2013: iii) shift the debate "towards the central place of citizens" and "decentralized, open urban infrastructures" to introduce new thinking about how people can share ideas and technologies globally. Discussing the smart city, Calzada and Cobo criticize its "technological determinism" and the assumptions that digital technology is enough to ensure smartness, recommending "unplugging" (2015: 23). In the same vein, as an alternative to "the dominant smart city discourse," Wilson and Chakraborty propose to include "collaborative planning" and "social learning" to counter "positivist tendencies to planning that dominated much of the twentieth century" (2019: 44).

Open governments typically offer open data facilities to encourage civil technology, smart citizenship, and collaboration. Sieber and Johnson analyze open data models, which they group in four types: a) the "data over the wall" model implies just publishing open data; b) the "code exchange" model supports the use of open data to fill concrete needs in local economic development; c) the "civic issue tracker" model accepts "direct feedback from citizens on a limited range of issues," and d) the "participatory open data" model implies the citizen co-production of data and promotes "transparency, rights and democratic objectives," and "social connectedness" (2015: 310–311). The first two models are mainly catered for the private sector, which influences the choices and

frequency of datasets, favoring the publication of the most commercially viable data (Sieber and Johnson, 2015: 314). The other models require a shifting role of the government, a "reflection on trust between government and citizens," and effective institutional responses to citizen expectations (Sieber and Johnson, 2015: 314). Making data available does not automatically entail open data re-utilization by other society sectors, including people and organized society. However, in a datafied environment dominated by big platforms, this is a crucial issue since actual democratic participation hinges on citizens' data agency (Gutierrez, 2019).

We draw from the transparency-participation-collaboration paradigm for open government (Geiger and von Lucke, 2012) to respond to the research questions.

The Transparency-participation-collaboration Framework

Transparency (related typically to accountability), participation (referring to shared knowledge and decision-making processes), and collaboration (understood as engagement with collaborative methods) are the basic principles of open government (Geiger and von Lucke, 2012). The Open Government Partnership (OGP) process of which Irekia is a partner uses similar terms as indicators to measure openness; *inform* occurs when the government offers information; *consult* happens when people provide inputs; *involve* refers to feedback on inputs, and *collaborate* indicates a dialogue takes place (OGP, 2019b). Among others (e.g., Sieber's and Johnson's models), these definitions entrench the ideas of transparency, participation, and collaboration.

Administrative transparency is a metaphor to refer to visibility that allows citizens to inspect governmental behavior; it implies access, communication, and accountability. In transparent governments, data are available in a way that makes them accessible to citizens, and officials are accountable for any misdeeds revealed by transparency (Goodrich, 2015; Izdebski, 2015). In 2019, 20 of the European countries (71 percent)

indicated that open data had "a high impact on government transparency and accountability," providing insights into "government expenditure" (European Data Portal, 2019). Examining Wellbeing Toronto —an open data, geographic information system tool—, Barber and MacLellan conclude that as open data become prevalent, a more varied understanding of municipal government organization may emerge (2019). This first characteristic refers to public, available, and accessible data.

However, data can be hard to find. "The State of Open Government Data in 2017" reports that data is often not readily usable (Global Open Data Index, 2017). Despite the relevance of transparency, from the 26 national portals that offer a data request option in Europe, only 14 of them —including Spain's and Open Data Euskadi— showcase these requests transparently (European Data Portal, 2019: 25).

While there is still a resistance to transparency, as Torres notes in Mexico (2020) and Hemmersam et al. observe in Norway (2016), some governments have embraced it without becoming more participative. Examples include Saudi Arabia's open data platform, which does not offer relevant information (Global Open Data Index, 2015), and China's statistic data website (Bernanke and Olso, 2016). A portal focussing on global testing during the pandemic notes that there were only "some data relating to parts of China" (Hasell et al., 2020), which do not qualify as open data. That is, the *open government* label is not enough to guarantee openness, participation, or collaboration. While transparency seemed enough for better governance in 2006 (Hood and Heald, 2006), years later, it is proved to be insufficient to generate trust (O'Hara, 2012), fight against corruption (Lindstedt and Naurin, 2010; Starke et al., 2016), or engender ethical behavior (Gelman, 2017). In some cases, open data are not enough to implement statistical research (Saxena and Muhammad, 2018).

In a previous exploration, participation in a datafied environment is defined in terms of lowering entry thresholds to facilitate citizen data agency (Gutierrez, 2019). Data agency –or the cognizant activity of transforming data into objects of everyday life (Gutierrez, 2019; Kennedy, 2016)— entails promoting data literacy, namely, the access to data, the skills, and the opportunities to participate in data processes. In the same vein, Wilson and Chakraborty also note that digital literacy is vital for democracy (2019: 44). Namely, this characteristic relates to transformative data.

Cases around the globe prove the existence of ordinary data agency. Gutierrez (2018) presents a taxonomy of dozens of data activism cases by people and organized society. However, most examples in Gutierrez (2018) rely on alternative data sources, including whistleblowers, crowdsourcing platforms gathering citizen data, scraping tools, and data generating methods (i.e., via sensors). Institutions highlight the importance of open data participation, but evidence of open data citizen participation is scarce. An OGP report, looking at micro-level evidence within its members, suggests that "greater public participation and access" can contribute to "a larger trend toward lowered corruption" but offers no examples (OGP, 2019b, para. 17). Looking at the City of New York's open data facility, Okamoto finds that it is not clear "how useable the data is for users without technical skills and resources" (2016: 1). Only 8 percent of the open data reusers in her study were non-profit civic organizations (Okamoto, 2016: 6). Irekia's website includes a participation space that allows people to send a petition, see the Basque Government's initiatives, and access its responses (Irekia, 2019). But "research on the relationship between economic growth and open government is considerably more developed than that of the other societal benefits" such as participation, admits OGP (2019b). Looking at two initiatives –ImproveMyCity and CloudFunding— in Thessaloniki, Greece, Komninos et al. conclude that participation and multi-actor decision-making are "smart

city plans" formulated exclusively by authorities (2018: 16), spotlighting the distance that exist between the *open* and *smart* labels and the reality of citizen participation.

While participating involves *joining in*, collaboration entails *working together*. Collaboration is supposed to improve the government's effectiveness by fostering partnerships within the government and other stakeholders, including third sector organizations and individuals. Although the latest European Data Portal's report talks about "maturity," it also highlights that there should be a new focus on quality, impact, and sharing (European Data Portal, 2019). Craglia et al. say that the European public sector must move from "pushing the data out," a *broadcasting* model, to "drawing the users in," an *interactive* model (2018: 110), a term that shows some intersection with the transformative data label seen earlier.

Observing the case of the City of Chicago, Kassen says that a collaboration with non-profit organizations such as Code for America –founded to help local governments—has been beneficial, as the city has received "significant technical assistance" (2013: 510). Kassen concludes that the philanthropic private non-profit sector "plays an important role in overall diffusion of the open data concept" (2013: 512). However, philanthropy in Europe is not as significant as in the US (CERPhi, 2015), and technical assistance is not the same as collaboration. Besides, transparency and collaboration can also "collide" if the latter is based on "data trade" (Peled, 2011). Looking at former US President Barack Obama's Open Data scheme, Peled highlights the clash between the freeing data mandate of the program and the interests of federal agencies trading data (2011). Although this observation is interesting, it does not apply to Irekia since it does not sell data.

While transparency was an essential element in open data facilities, participation and collaboration are comparatively novel and less established. Many open data facilities make data available, but it is uncertain whether they are transformative or interactive.

This situation influences engagement and collaboration in open data initiatives worldwide, including Irekia. Besides, there is a trade-off between releasing data and financing its production. Most of the re-utilization is for-profit as data provide an income stream. Sometimes, exclusive rights are given to organizations that tidy up the data and market them for profit, clashing with the transparency principle. This may happen because the gains from participation and collaboration are not sufficiently established to justify rejecting for-profit open data business models. However, this question goes beyond this analysis's scope.

The Basque Experience

The open data concept review is timely as the Basque open government apparatus is in review as part of the Open Government Partnership (OGP, 2019c). OGP gathers government leaders and civil society advocates from 78 countries and entities to promote "accountable, responsive and inclusive governance" (OGP, 2019a). The Basque cities of Vitoria-Gasteiz, Bilbao, and San Sebastian –on which different administrative layers at autonomous government, province, and city levels intersect— provide the backdrop.

Despite Basque separatist terrorism killing about one thousand people from 1959 to 2018, institutional, social, and economic stability exists. Euskadi –a small and prosperous autonomous region in Northern Spain where about 2.2 million people live— experienced the lowest economic downfall in Spain during the crisis that started in 2007 (Ortega, 2014). Irekia was set up in 2009 to foster transparency, participation, and collaboration (Irekia, 2019).

Open Data Euskadi, the platform operated by Irekia, offers data from the six Basque provincial and capital administrations, and operates independently. It collaborates with the Spanish open data facility, which gathers all the data that local and regional institutions have opened; Open Data Euskadi does not offer data from other territories.

Irekia pioneered open data. In 2011, for example, the Organization of American States (OAS) signed a contract with the Basque Government so that its 44 member countries could use its open-source code and adapt it to their needs to create their platforms (Gonzalo, 2012). The open government culture is widespread in Euskadi. Dyntra –an international collaborative platform that measures openness in organizations— ranks the three Basque capitals in positions first, second, and fourth among the most open cities in Spain (2019).

However, ten years after the Basque open data facility launch, the level of data re-utilization by citizens and organized society is low since most open data re-utilizers are companies pursuing for-profit applications, according to our interviewees, who include Irekia's managers. This problem is common in other open data platforms. For example, tackling the level of open data reuse in Spain, the European Data Portal refers only to the "economic and social value of companies that reuse data from the public or private sector to create added value products" (2019: 47), with no mention of the third sector or people. According to ASEDIE, the number of companies reusing open data in Spain increased in 2018 by 3.7 percent (Asociación Multisectorial de la Información, 2018); nevertheless, ASEDIE does not record open data re-utilization by ordinary people and non-profits. Some of the datasets offered by Open Data Euskadi have been downloaded more than a thousand times, but its reutilization is not clear as people's usage does not appear in official reports. This study examines citizens' and organized society's use of open data from the Basque portal for the first time.

Methods Section

The main research question is, "How can actionable open data be defined?" To respond, this study addresses the specific questions:

RQ1: What do minders, reusers of, and experts on open data say about how open data should be?

RQ2: What does an analysis of 78 cases of re-utilization of open data from the Basque facility say about actionable open data?

RQ3: Are there any significant differences between responses to RQ1 and RQ2?

RQ4: Are there any disparities between what the data collected say before and after the COVID-19 pandemic struck Spain?

We use mixed methods, including participant observation, semi-structured interviews, and an analysis of open data projects. The intention is to zoom in on real-life experiences and perceptions of data by ordinary people, organizations, and experts.

Participant Observation

Participant observation is employed to collect data from the meetings, discussions, and internal documents behind a workshop. Participant observation grants researchers an advantaged understanding of processes' workings as they take place (Balsiger and Lambelet, 2014: 146). This method is particularly suitable because it disturbs the appearance of uniformity in collective behavior. For example, although the workshop was a convergence of like-minded people at first glance, the debates soon revealed the tensions in the room between old and new, grassroots/citizens and top-down, and local, regional, and national levels.

We gathered panelists' presentations and exchanges with the audience during a workshop entitled #datuirekiak (*#opendata* in Basque), held from November 13 to 15, 2019, in San Sebastian. The gathering attracted representatives from the public sector at city, province, autonomous region, and national levels and around sixty scholars, activists, and citizens. The workshop was organized by Irekia (the Basque open government platform), Hirikilabs (a citizen laboratory that promotes the collaborative use of technology), and the University of Deusto. The workshop was facilitated by Montera34, an organization that generates open events, code, and design for social

projects. Up to a point, the interviews are a follow-up of the participant observation of the workshop since five of the interviewees took part in it.

Semi-structured Interviews

Following a criterion sampling approach (Patton, 2014), the interviewees were selected for their close association with open data infrastructures and open government. Table 1 lists their profiles. This selection focuses on capturing what decision-makers, practitioners, minders, reusers, and experts think and how they employ open data. The semi-structured interviews allow comparisons and help understand how interviewees make sense of their world (Bernard, 2006: 210).

The interview questionnaire included questions such as: "How should open data be?" "Which role should open data have in society?" "How were open pandemic data useful?" We did up to five rounds of questions with these reusers before the pandemic's first wave and after the third wave, from November 27, 2019, to February 16, 2021, to capture information about the relevance of open pandemic data. The idea is to explore their ideas about the broader role of open data taking advantage of the new awareness about their role during the pandemic.

Table 1: List of interviewees, their roles and the interviewing times and dates

Interviewees	Role	Interviewing dates
Interviewee 1	Civil servant with responsibilities over open government structures in Aragón	November, 2019; June, 2020
Interviewee 2	University professor, researcher and data activist from Valencia	November, 2019
Interviewee 3	Civil servant with responsibilities over open data in the Basque Country	November, 2019; June, 2020; February, 2021
Interviewee 4	Head of a data and design company in Spain	November, 2019; June, 2020
Interviewee 5	Civil servant in charge of a culture and technology project in the Basque Country	December, 2019; June, 2020

Interviewee 6	Data scientist and researcher at a private foundation in San Sebastian	January, 2020; June, 2020; February, 2021
Interviewee 7	Data activist, IT and media expert at a private company that works with open source in the Basque Country	February, 2020; February, 2021
Interviewee 8	Expert on open source technology at a cooperative in Gipuzkoa	February, 2020; June, 2020; February, 2021
Interviewee 9	Free software developer at a cooperative in Gipuzkoa	February, 2020; June, 2020
Interviewee 10	Civil servant with responsibilities over open government structures in Euskadi	June, 2020
Interviewee 11	Local journalist specialized in health data	June, 2020
Interviewee 12	Representative of a data volunteers association in Euskadi	June, 2020
Interviewee 13	Civil servant with responsibilities over transparency structures in Aragón	June, 2020
Interviewee 14	Data journalist working nationally in Spain	June, 2020
Interviewee 15	Data and communication researcher and university professor	June, 2020; February, 2021

Case Comparison

The data collection is enriched by comparing 78 proposals submitted to the Open Data Ideas Awards organized by Open Data Euskadi in 2015, 2018, and 2020 amid the pandemic. All the open data-based projects have urban functions, addressing mobility, public services, environmental sensing, and health issues.

These awards were launched to publicize the existence of open data catalogs, showcase their potential, and encourage their re-utilization (Irekoa, 2018). The competition rewards the best ideas for reusing open data and the best projects that provide services or web applications (Irekoa, 2018). Through mechanisms such as competitions, "the partnership with a non-governmental sector offers a more flexible result-oriented way of decision-making" (Kassen 2013: 512).

For this comparison, we draw from Desouza's and Bhagwatwar's study of open data applications set up by "citizens" to solve diverse urban problems in areas such as mobility and public utilities (2012). These authors classify cases using various parameters capturing information on who the developer is, launch year and location, purpose, and website. However, it is unclear whether individuals and civil society organizations set up the initiatives without state or business intervention. Most of them seem for-profits². For example, the taxonomy includes Asthmapolis³, an inhaler company providing asthma treatment and commercial services, and Zonability⁴, a private company providing housing. For clarity's sake, these companies would not qualify as citizen initiatives in our study since they are not non-profits. Sustainability is also key to any endeavor aiming to last. However, the idea here is to examine the nature of citizen-driven projects in the Basque open data ecosystem to define actionable open data. In our study, we have introduced new questions. "Does it use other datasets?" refers to other sets apart from the ones available at Open Data Euskadi. "Does it consider for-profit aspects?" refers to whether the project includes information about how to obtain economic gain. "Who is the final beneficiary?" states who the final recipients are. "Does it propose to open new datasets?" talks about whether the project demands that Open Data Euskadi opens new datasets. This does not imply the government later gave those data to participants, as we do not know; it shows that it would have been necessary to open more datasets to develop the proposed idea properly. We also looked at whether the projects were operative and until when. When they are not, we cannot say whether this has to do with the lack of extra open data, but this is another information layer pointing at the sustainability of open data projects and open data usefulness. This analysis also looks at the typologies of private

² Many of these applications are no longer available at the time of writing, so these authors could not check them all.

³ See <https://www.mobihealthnews.com/25255/asthmapolis-now-propeller-moves-beyond-asthma>.

⁴ See <https://www.zonability.com/company>.

companies submitting projects according to their size, based on the European Commission Recommendation's definition of micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (EUR-Lex, 2003), as we understand there is a distance between a multinational corporation and a local start-up trying to monetize open data.

Results and Analysis

This section summarizes the results of the workshop's analysis, the interviews, and the open data-based initiatives. Table 2 shows the projects submitted in 2015, 2018, and 2020. We have used the transparency-participation-collaboration paradigm and the research questions to organize the analysis. The answers to the questions are unbalanced since we have found more relevant ideas about transparency than the other two open government elements, mirroring concerns outlined in the theoretical section.

Table 2: Comparison of proposals submitted to the Open Data ideas awards in 2015, 2018 and 2020

	Project	Topic	Does it use other datasets?	Who presented it?	Does it consider direct for profit aspects?	Who is the final beneficiary?	Does it propose to open new datasets?	Was / is it operational? (Period)
2015	Data Sense	Data	Yes	Private company (SL, microenterprise)	Yes	Private companies	No	No
	Euskadi Open Aggregator	Data	Yes	Private company (S Cooperativa, small company)	No	Public administration/private companies/NGOs/citizens	No	No
	Aparkatu	Mobility	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
	Deporte en Euskadi	Leisure	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
	Geolocalizad or de Postales	Tourism	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
	Guía Interactiva por GPS	Tourism	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
	Trip2Bilbao	Tourism	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
	Básico Estudio Nuevo	Business	Yes	Individual	No	Private companies	No	No

Comercio (BENC)							
Precepción del mercado Marítimo Vasco (PMMV)	Business	Yes	Individual	No	Private companies/citizens	No	No
Dónde Reciclo	Environment	Yes	Private company (SL, microenterprise)	No	Citizens	Yes	No
Donejakue app	Tourism	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
Plataforma para la Gobernanza y la Participación Ciudadana	Public services	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	Yes	No
Turismo Accesible Euskadi	Tourism	No	Individual	No	Citizens	Yes	No
Cartilla de vacunación digital	Health	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	Yes	No
Política medioambiental al servicio de la ciudadanía	Environment	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens/public administration	No	No
Apoyo	Democracy	No	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
CalidApp – "tu calidad de vida"	Health	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	Yes	No
¿Violentan los datos abiertos la privacidad del voto en las elecciones?	Democracy	Yes	Research group UPV	No	Citizens/researchers/politicians	Yes	No
Elige tus estudios con proyección de futuro	Education	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	Yes	No
Meantime. Lee mientras viajas.	Leisure	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
Experiencia cultural personalizada	Leisure	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
openGida	Public services	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	Yes	No
Salud 24 horas	Health	Yes	Private non-profit foundation	No	Citizens	Yes	No
El "open data" necesita del "open community"	Data	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens/NGOs/public administration	Yes	No
Osakidetza Hurbil	Health	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No

	Hacia soluciones adaptadas de movilidad en virtud de la diversidad funcional de la población residente en Euskadi	Mobility	No	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
	Sistema para evitar atascos en carreteras y ciudades de Euskadi	Mobility	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens/public administration	Yes	No
	Análisis del impacto de eventos culturales y de ocio a través de las redes sociales: #BBKLive2015 y #Astenagusia 2015	Leisure	Yes	Research institution (related to Basque Government)	No	Private companies/public administration	No	No
	iBILI – Buscador Inteligente de Licitaciones	Public services	Yes	Individual	Yes	Private companies/public administration	No	No
	Becas en Euskadi	Public services	No	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
	Euskadi Transparente	Democracy	No	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
	EuskalFaunaApp	Environment	Yes	Private company (SL, big)	No	Citizens	No	No
	Herramienta para fomento de un modelo de turismo responsable en la CAV	Tourism	Yes	Individual	Yes	Tourists/citizens/private companies/public administration	No	No
2018	OPE Euskadi	Employment	No	Individual	Yes	Citizens	No	No
	Estudios y empleabilidad	Employment	No	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
	Escapada por Bilbao y alrededores para el turista del siglo XXI	Tourism	No	Individual	No	Citizens	Yes	Beta version / sample. Currently operational, not available the start date.
	D-PURA: Depuración y Provisión de Unidades de Recogida de Agua	Public services	No	Individual	Yes	Public administration	No	No
	Adjudicación de	Public services	Yes	Private company (SL, big)	No	Private companies	No	No

	licitaciones públicas							
	Lagundoo-Ayudas y subvenciones	Public services	Yes	Individual	Yes	Citizens/NGOs/private companies	No	No
	Euskal Travelling	Tourism	Yes	Individual	Yes	Citizens	No	No
	Bisita	Leisure	Yes	Private company (SL, microenterprise)	No	Citizens	Yes	No
	Ibilorpen - Euskadiko ibilbide eta paseoen aplikazioa	Leisure	Yes	Private company (SL, small)	Yes	Citizens	No	No
	Urrea: minería de datos	Data	No	Private company (SL, microenterprise)	Yes	Citizens/NGOs/private companies/public administration	No	No
	Rutéate	Tourism	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
	Detección de objetos mediante cámaras de tráfico	Mobility	Yes	Individual	No	Public administration	Yes	No
	Observatorio geográfico de oportunidades de empleo	Employment	No	Individual	No	Citizens/private companies	Yes	No
	MyWave	Leisure	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
	BIAS - De todos, para todos	Public services	Yes	Individual	Yes	Citizens/NGOs/private companies	No	No
2020	Índice de Movilidad en el Transporte Público de Bilbao	Mobility	No	Individual	No	Public administration	No	No
	Hotelbot Euskadi	Tourism ^	Yes	Individual	Yes	Citizens	No	No
	Ondarea.eus	Democracy	Yes	Private non-profit association	No	Citizens	Yes	Yes. Currently operational, not available the start date.
	Gure bidexkak	Environment / leisure *	Yes	Individual	Yes	Citizens	Yes	No
	Bam bú	Environment / beauty	Yes	Individual	Yes	Citizens	No	No
	EuskoNaTour	Tourism	Yes	Private company (S. Coop. microenterprise)	No	Citizens	No	Beta version / sample available from November 10, 2020 to the present.
	Planak Euskadin	Leisure *	Yes	Individual	Yes	Citizens	Yes	No

Damaraua	Education	Yes	Private company (S. Coop, big? HUHEZI)	No	Citizens/Public Administration	Yes	No
Euskadi Emprende	Business ^	Yes	Individual	Yes	Private companies/Public Administration	No	No
Praktikadi	Education/Business *	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens/private companies	Yes	No
Udal Future	Public services	No	Individual	No	Public Administration	Yes	No
Ortu as a Service (OaaS)	Environment	No	Individual	No	Citizens	Yes	No
Pronóstico de Polen Estacional de Euskadi	Health	No	Individual	No	Citizens	Yes	No
Smart Bike Sharing	Mobility	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	Yes	No
Actividad física para la ciudadanía	Health/leisure	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
Recomendación turística COVID-free	Tourism *	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No
Oferta educativa ESPO / Hezkuntza Eskaintza DBHO	Education	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	Yes	No
LANDARA. Vivir en un entorno rural en tiempos del coronavirus	Environment *	Yes	Private company (SLU, microenterprise)	No	Citizens	No	No
Playas de Euskadi / Euskadiko Hondartzak	Leisure	Yes	Individual	Yes	Citizens	No	No
Data Irekia	Data	No	Individual	No	NGOs	No	No
Aurrekontua pp	Public services *	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	Yes	No
Berritsu - Avatar para lectura de datos abiertos de avisos o noticias	Public services	Yes	Individual	Yes	Citizens	Yes	No
Recomendación Inteligente Empleo/Candidato - Lanbide	Employment *	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens/private companies	No	No
Sistema de predicción e inferencia de precios de alquiler de vivienda en la CAV	Housing	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No

Ongi etorri Euskal Herrira	Tourism	Yes	Individual	Yes	Citizens	Yes	No
OpenOlvidata	Mobility	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	Yes	No
Desarrollo de herramienta de predicción de roturas de tuberías de agua para el País Vasco	Public services	Yes	Private company (SLU, microenterprise)	No	Citizens/public administrations	No	No
Mejora de la empleabilidad tras el impacto de la pandemia	Employment *	Yes	Private company (SL, big)	No	Citizens	No	No
Sanikadi	Education/health *	Yes	Individual	No	Education centers	No	No
Naturgida - Natur ingurunea bultzatu, babestu eta zabaltzeko gida	Leisure *	Yes	Individual	No	Citizens	No	No

Source: elaborated by the authors. * means COVID-19 was an important aspect when developing the idea, while ^ means it was a variable, but not an essential one.

Transparency: Necessary but Incomplete

RQ1: What do minders, reusers of, and experts on open data say about how open data should be from a transparency's perspective?

In activism, data usefulness is required for transparency to be consequential (Gutierrez, 2018). Interviewee 1 (a civil servant with responsibilities over open government) concurs. "Just open data don't work. Let's move from a paradigm of available data to transformative data," he says. Interviewees 1, 4 (a data and design expert), 6 (a data scientist and researcher), and 7 (a data scientist) express similar ideas regarding the usefulness that should be embedded in transparency.

Transparency is perceived as having positive outcomes; Interviewee 9 (a free source developer) says, for instance, that open data can generate "peace of mind" by helping fight the "clickbait journalism and the untruthful news shared on social media platforms." Public and published open data "facilitate the creation of more data" (Interviewee 8) and foster knowledge (Interviewee 9).

Another idea connected to transparency is the management of expectations; Sieber and Johnson note that "citizens expect that government will be receptive to their contributions," acting on them and that available data are speedy, complete, and accurate (2015: 314). But that is not always true, as Interviewee 1 notes: "When (young people) demand something from an administration, they expect an answer which is instantaneous, ubiquitous, and universal, and establishes a bidirectional relationship." So, when that does not happen, the relationship between citizen-government can be damaged. Meanwhile, governments engaging in open data assume that citizens will use public data in appropriate ways and that a relationship of trust is recognized (Sieber and Johnson, 2015: 314).

The way data are released is essential for transparency to work; Interviewee 6 states that open data would be more valuable "if they were presented in complete historical series, in a stable API (an application program interface) and with no erratum." Nevertheless, "public, published, and open data" are not the same thing, says Interviewee 8 (an expert on open-source technologies). In 2015, a group of activists of the ILP Eskola Inklusiboa—an organization for inclusiveness in the Basque education system—, supported by Montera34, visualized official data to reveal the inequalities in Euskadi between public and private schools receiving public subsidies. They employed datasets published on a PDF report (Consejo Escolar de Euskadi, 2015), which were not available in an open format, to look at where international students (mostly from migrant families) went. To use the data, they had to transform the tables on PDF documents into reusable formats and map the school zones, which were not available (Montera34, 2015).

An obstacle for transparency that lingered in the workshop and was apparent in some interviews (e.g., with Interviewees 1 and 3) is the lack of buy-in within administrative echelons. Open data enthusiasts in the administration complain about lack

of a) support, knowledge, or interest from politicians making decisions at the top; b) cooperation from other departments that oversee data collection; c) standardized systems, and d) mechanisms to integrate citizens' inputs.

How can governments pre-emptively determine what data will be helpful? Some data portals in Europe monitor reuser behavior, impact, and popular datasets to understand how to be more helpful (European Data Portal, 2019). But more analysis is needed. "We do liberate open data in massive amounts, but we need civic knowledge to open what is needed," says Interviewee 10. Interviewee 1 suggests that a new role in the public administration, the *community builder*, would help transform the institutions from within to overcome these problems.

Since usefulness cannot be anticipated, it seems transparency should be practiced by default; public officials in the workshop and the interviews admit as much. Interviewee 5 (a civil servant in charge of a culture and data project) believes that "open data is a (civic) right per se," which means that "as long as it is possible, all the data generated should be open by default." Interviewee 7 says that the administration's "public information has been paid for by citizens," so "the administration must open all data."

RQ2: What does an analysis of 78 cases of re-utilization of open data from the Basque facility say about actionable open data from a transparency's perspective?

Our analysis of the submissions to the Open Data awards supports the notion that citizens do not find everything they need in the open data vaults: only 15 of the 78 initiatives examined (19.2 percent) rely just on Open Data Euskadi's datasets. This means most of the projects are also based on private data or open datasets from other organizations.

RQ3: Are there any significant differences between responses to RQ1 and RQ2?

Some of the experts' and reusers' views are reinforced by examining the projects from transparency since they point to a need for more open datasets. A total of 28 of the 78

projects (35.9 percent) propose, explicitly or implicitly, that Open Data Euskadi offer new datasets to develop their idea. Even though it is not a majority, there is an awareness about the benefits of opening more data and about public institutions' responsibility.

RQ4: Are there any disparities between what the data collected say before and after the COVID-19 pandemic struck Spain?

Montera³⁴'s school subsidies report and the projects submitted to the Open Data awards were not urgent, but what happens when the need for data transparency is dire? Interviewee 11 (a local data journalist) says that pandemic open data were offered in a non-systematic manner initially and that it took some time before the Open Data Euskadi updates became regular. But he notes that, once updates became systematic:

The problem was that the same information was not always available, the criteria were changed regularly, and some of the data offered as authenticated previously were later modified. One of the basic statistics principles is that data should be comparable, which has not always been possible⁵.

Apart from disaggregated data by province vanishing one day, other hiccups were that health authorities stopped offering hospitalized patients' data, which included information on the people in intensive care units (López, 2020). The criteria to classify the data on people recovered or discharged changed too (López, 2020). "It has now been acknowledged that some recovered patients were deceased," says Interviewee 11. Despite these problems, he notes that the datasets were offered in various formats, including PDF, Word, Excel, JSON, and XML—, which was helpful. Interviewee 15 (a data and communication researcher) concurs. Nevertheless, Interviewee 6—who used data on JSON format— reports that sometimes Open Data Euskadi changed the format without

⁵ "El problema es que no siempre se ha dado la misma información, que se han cambiado los criterios de manera habitual y que los datos dados como seguros en días anteriores se han ido modificando. Uno de los principios básicos de la estadística es que sea comparable, y eso no ha sido siempre posible" (Interviewee 11).

warning, datasets were introduced hurriedly, with erratum, and data from other territories were mistakenly included. Interviewee 15 complains that data were not contextualized, hindering interpretation. Of the nine datasets related to COVID-19 offered by Open Data Euskadi, as of June 3, 2020, only four had been updated regularly (daily, weekly, or monthly), while five of them were available only for the city of San Sebastian. By February 22, 2021, 33 of the 44 datasets related to the pandemic were offered by San Sebastian, indicating that most of the available open data correspond just to part of the territory.

Interviewee 11 and another fellow journalist –feeding maps and search engines with hospital occupation, nursing homes, and intensive care unit data on their newspaper's website— had to make "continuous adjustments to the datasets" and even remove entire charts because a data type was no longer supplied. But the data visualization section was a favorite with their publics, "so we understand that it has helped people, or at least offered a better understanding of the pandemic."

Change in data format is common, and most governments have problems anticipating needs because data suppliers are not always data users; besides, the pandemic put extra pressure on open data facilities. But it is uncertain from the interviews whether the dataset format changes were something pandemic-specific or the norm at Open Data Euskadi. Interviewee 6 does not know how the open data facility operated before the pandemic; Interviewee 7 could not observe significant changes; Interviewee 15 believes changing formats and disappearing datasets have been a recurring problem. The interviewed officers hold a different view. Some structural challenges may have influenced the quality of the data released during the pandemic. For example, Interviewee 10 admits that, during the lockdown, Osakidetza did not systematically provide data, but:

... in response to the pandemic's urgency, I think that we opened good and trustworthy data appropriately. This effort generated (internally) much manual work. And I think these data have been useful. Almost all the news media outlets developed infographics to comment on the day-to-day evolution.⁶

Interviewee 10 (a civil servant with overseeing responsibilities) highlights that it was a changing situation and that experts recommended that R0 figures were better offered aggregated given Euskadi's small population (2.18 million people distributed in three territories and 251 municipalities). Offering data per city was out of the question since in small towns, "people would know who died of COVID-19 by the lack of a funeral," says Interviewee 10. He adds that Open Data Euskadi was congratulated for being the only autonomous government noticing an excess of mortality, which later was confirmed by the National Monitoring System of Daily Mortality. Interviewee 3 (a civil servant with responsibilities over open data) explains that the gaps and the adjustments were due to a redesign of the datasets at a national level and an adaption to World Health Organization standards, not up to Open Data Euskadi.

The problems highlighted by Interviewee 6, 11, and 15 are not unique to Open Data Euskadi; nationally, the indicators showing contagion cases and fatalities kept on changing. Andrino et al. highlight 15 glitches in national updates, including unstandardized and incoherent data (2020). Although the daily appraises in press conferences and reports continued, the Spanish COVID-19 portal stopped being updated daily (Centro Nacional de Epidemiología, 2020). According to Interviewee 14 (a data journalist), the datasets in Spain shifted while the pandemic was evolving, making their analysis and visualization "impossible." There were problems around accessibility,

⁶ "Creo que abrimos datos buenos y veraces de la manera adecuada. Esto generó (internamente) mucho trabajo manual. Y creo que estos datos han sido útiles. De hecho, casi todos los medios de comunicación desarrollaron infografías para comentar el día a día de la evolución".

interpretation, and time consistency (Interviewee 14). According to Interviewee 13 (a civil servant with responsibilities over transparency in another autonomy), there were significant data discrepancies among Spanish territories. According to Interviewee 8, governments only volunteered data when these data supported their decisions.

COVID-19 has shown how crucial transparency can be; as Interviewee 11 says, "from the beginning, data (and specifically accurate data) became essential to make decisions and interpret facts around us." Today, transparency "should be a way to do things" in the administration, summarizes Interviewee 3.

Participation: Towards a More Active Role of Citizens

What happens when people re-utilize open data? Sometimes, the results of open data exploration might not be what the authorities expect. ILP Eskola Inklusiboa report revealed inequalities between the public and private education systems in Euskadi (Montera34, 2015). Although Montera34 would like to revise the report, the PDFs on which this analysis was based were not updated. If participation hinges on access to datasets and the incorporation of data reusers' inputs, the first thing that needs to happen is that data are provided in usable formats when organizations such as ILP Eskola Inklusiboa demand them.

RQ1: What do experts on, minders, and reusers of open data say about how open data should be from a participation's perspective?

Participation entails proactivity. Interviewee 4 (head of a data and design company) believes that "the responsibility of reusing open data should not lie just with citizens," implying that governments should encourage people to employ them.

However, it seems that some of the interviewees and the workshop participants believe cases such as ILP Eskola Inklusiboa –exhibiting its data agency by demanding public data and reusing them— are exceptions. According to Interviewee 1, a frequent issue is that "currently there is more participation offer than (citizen) demand." This is an

idea that also came up during the workshop. The alleged lack of open data curiosity on the part of citizens and organizations might happen because "there is no open data culture in Spain, citizens are neither informed nor formed" about the opportunities of open data (Interviewee 5).

RQ2: What does an analysis of 78 cases of re-utilization of open data from the Basque facility say about actionable open data from a participation's perspective?

Contrary to what reusers, data minders, and experts think, a total of 61 of the 78 initiatives were submitted by individuals, most of them with social purposes.

Only one of the individual proposals was designed to benefit just private companies, while another nine initiatives were planned to benefit private companies plus citizens, NGOs, or public administrations. Although this is not a statistically relevant sample of citizens and organized society reusing open data, it is significant that most of them were citizen initiatives with social goals.

RQ3: Are there any significant differences between responses to RQ1 and RQ2?

The ideas emerging from the experts and reusers interviews seem to clash with the ideas from the projects. The difference between the perception of a lack of interest in open data among citizens and what the projects' analysis reveals is noteworthy. It means there is more appetite for open data participation than what is recognized at an institutional or expert level. The examples of ILP Eskola Inklusiboa and the experiences of Hirikilabs and Montera³⁴, who have incubated, guided, and enabled dozens of citizen data projects in workshops over the past few years, seem to confirm this idea.

RQ4: Are there any disparities between what the data collected say before and after the COVID-19 pandemic struck Spain?

The pandemic made data participation popular. According to Interviewee 10, "it is the first-time people are demanding so unanimously that we release a dataset." This speaks

of how citizens envision themselves as participants when data are relevant. Interviewee 12 (representative of a data volunteers association in Euskadi) believes that, during the pandemic, open data was the basis for information and intelligence creation in many sectors. The association employed open data to fight against disinformation, organize the association's work, and make a workflow forecast.

Yet not all the projects presented in 2020 were related to the pandemic. Only ten of the 33 ideas were explicitly proposed to address the situation provoked by COVID-19, and another two mentioned the pandemic as a non-essential variable. This corroborates the idea that the interest in open data existed before the pandemic, which introduced new ways of using data and awareness.

Collaboration: The Challenge Today

RQ1: What do experts on, minders, and reusers of open data say about how open data should be from a collaboration's perspective?

Interviewees 2 (a university professor), 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, and 10 support citizens' rights to intervene in data processes. Interviewee 9 proposes a "local data observatory" composed of organized citizens and open data movement's agents to help collective decision-making. Open data's final aim, according to Interviewee 4, is not "citizens using them" but "political change" achieved through processes in which ordinary people are agents. Interviewee 5 agrees; the collaboration among "citizens, media, public administration, universities, and private organizations" might be vital for open data's transformative power. Interviewees 2 and 8 think collaboration in open data can contribute to a fairer and more democratic society. Citizen collaboration in open data could also become a tool to reduce data monopolization by commercial platforms, contributing to data sovereignty (Interviewee 4).

There is consensus among the interviewed experts and reusers that citizens' collaboration is fundamental if open data is destined to solve citizens' problems. However,

collaboration is the area where more challenges and less evidence are identified. According to Interviewee 10, Open Data Euskadi is amenable to citizens' inputs "to learn together," but "we expect that the intermediary sector can help us set up an informal dialogue to hone our open data instruments and processes."

RQ2: What does an analysis of 78 cases of re-utilization of open data from the Basque facility say about actionable open data from a collaboration's perspective?

The level of civic collaboration with the Basque public administration can be tested by looking at the Open Data awards. Even if the sample is not big enough to generalize, the analysis shows that citizens are interested in open data and that their ideas focus not on political change but on solving concrete social, urban issues. The main four topics that concern individual projects include tourism (13), public services (12), leisure (12), and mobility, health, and environment (7 projects each). Nearly all of them have local or regional purposes.

Although many of the projects use data not found in the open data facility, only 29 projects propose that the administration opens new datasets. If there is more open data exigence than apparent, but data agents do not voice that demand, it can indicate that a breakdown in communication between public administrations and potential data re-utilizers exists.

Finally, the companies' typology is significant since seven out of 13 private entities were microenterprises, while two were small, and four were big firms. The lack of interest of big and medium-sized companies can be explained by the relatively small award (4,000 or 2,000 euros for the first and second prizes) and the fact that big corporations can generate their data and the means to exploit them. However, it is interesting as only three out of 13 projects presented by private companies introduce for-

profit aspects to the idea. This could indicate interest in collaboration from the third sector and social problem-solving using the Basque open data facility.

RQ3: Are there any significant differences between responses to RQ1 and RQ2?

In the workshop and the interviews, experts and reusers highlight the interest of collaboration for democracy, social change, and problem-solving, while the cases indicate a focus on the latter. The interviews also reveal an awareness about the importance of intermediaries to foster collaboration (which is not captured by the projects' analysis). In contrast, the proposals' analysis offers a glimpse at how collaboration can look like when proponents express their need for more datasets or determine what issues could be tackled.

RQ4: Are there any disparities between what the data collected say before and after the COVID-19 pandemic struck Spain?

The disparities between the data collected before and after the pandemic are difficult to spot since collaboration is the less established element. During the pandemic, some data reusers realized that the government's open data were not enough and created reusable datasets by collaborating with others. For example, Montera34 updated the COVID-19 data by Spanish provinces with 15 volunteers' support on the ground (Montera34, 2020). Their data were then used in a scientific article (Briz-Redón and Serrano-Aroca, 2020). Figure 2 shows a pandemic data visualization by province by Montera34 (@numeroteca⁷).

Other individuals and organizations, such as VostEuskadi⁸ –an association of digital emergency volunteers— and EuskadiCovid19⁹ –a group that analyzes the pandemic data— have also been working on communicating pandemic data locally.

⁷ See <https://twitter.com/numeroteca>, followed by 6 thousand people by February 26, 2021 on Twitter.

⁸ See <https://www.vosteuskadi.org/> and <https://twitter.com/VOSTeuskadi>, followed by 13,200 people by February 26, 2021 on Twitter.

⁹ See <https://twitter.com/Covid19Euskadi>, followed by 6,000 people by February 26, 2021 on Twitter.

Miguel Angel Reinoso's¹⁰ and Francesc Pujol's¹¹ Twitter feeds offer more pandemic data visualizations nationally. The popularity of these feeds has transformed them into influencers and policy advisers of sorts.

Figure 2: A visualization of disaggregated data by province on the pandemic in Spain using open data. Source: <https://lab.montera34.com/covid19/provincias.html>

Besides, Montera34 is behind the manifesto supporting open pandemic data at the national level (DatosCOVID19, 2020). Whether governments at national and regional levels have taken note and incorporated these contributions to increase collaboration or not is unclear.

Sustainability is an issue. None of the 78 projects were fully operative or publicly available at the time of writing. Two of them were available in a beta version. Another pending issue is the possibility of real-time decision-making based on data (referring specifically to tracking applications), according to Interviewee 10.

¹⁰ See <https://twitter.com/mianrey>, followed by 48,100 people by February 26, 2021 on Twitter.

¹¹ See @NewsReputation, followed by 36.3 thousand people by February 26, 2021 on Twitter.

Discussion

Although some of the interviews suggest otherwise, the analysis of the projects submitted to the Open Data awards and the information gathered about pandemic data's employment imply that open data are more relevant than anticipated. Our study is limited in two ways: first, we do not know who is behind the individual proposals, and second, the number of people we interviewed is limited. However, it shows citizens' and organized society's interest in open data is higher than the expert interviewees expected.

The pandemic created a before-and-after moment for data usage, too (Phillips and Barretto Briso, 2020). Beyond the Basque Country, many are recognizing the role of open data at a time of crisis; one example is the decision by a Brazilian supreme court judge to order premier Jair Bolsonaro's administration to resume publishing complete COVID-19 statistics (Phillips and Barretto Briso, 2020).

How can actionable open data be defined, then? Actionable open data a) are offered in an open and consistent format; b) generate relevant reuse; c) are encompassing enough to include all administration data by default, except for delicate and personal data, complying with data regulation; d) embed mechanisms for interaction and the integration of citizens and organized society in all phases of the data value chain, including the design, mining, analysis, and visualization; e) enable data agency by promoting data literacy –including access to data, skills, means, and opportunities— among individual citizens, governments, and social organizations; f) encourage alliances among various sectors for open data re-utilization with social aims; and g) respond to citizens' and organizations' needs and interests. This definition could serve as a guideline. Transformed into a set of questions (e.g., "Do these data enable data agency by promoting data literacy among individual citizens, governments, and social organizations?"), it could provide a framework for application in other open data environments.

We propose that open data moves from available to actionable data. Sieber and Johnson say that "accepting citizen input may require the government to move outside of strongly regulated and entrenched procedures" (2015: 6). To do that, governments need to generate trust and support citizens, for example, integrating citizen contributions into government hierarchies (Sieber and Johnson, 2015: 6). The concept of actionable data goes further by embedding data literacy promotion among citizens and government so that actionable data are released.

Echoing the criticism of smart city solutions' determinism (Calzada and Cobo, 2015; Wilson and Chakraborty, 2019), this analysis ultimately shows that just making data available is not enough. This study reveals tensions between a) the actual conditions in which open data supporters work within the administration and the expectations and needs generated in times of an emergency; b) the perceptions of a lack of curiosity or need on the part of citizens and the genuine interest exposed by the projects submitted to the Open Data awards, and c) the data literacy of people and the challenges of data agency.

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